

The potential therapeutic effects of Ginger in COVID-19 and other similar infections: A molecular review

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Abbreviations:

Ang: Angiotensin

ACE: Angiotensin converting enzyme

RAS: Renin-angiotensin system

Th: T helper

IL: Interleukin

CCL: Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand

TNF: Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha

CXCL: The chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand

G-CSF: Granulocyte-colony stimulating factor

IFN: Interferon

TGF: Transforming growth factor beta

NF- κ B: Nuclear factor Kappa B

FTL: ferritin light chain

Nrf2: nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2

HO-1: heme oxygenase-1

Trx1: thioredoxin 1

TrxR1: Thioredoxin reductase 1

AKR1B10: Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10

GCTLA4: γ -glutamyltransferase-like activity4

NQO1: Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate

GCLM: Glutamate-cysteine ligase modifier subunit

GCLC: Glutamate-cysteine ligase catalytic subunit

ARDS: Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome

Abstract

The current widespread pandemic due to SARS-CoV-2 infection has imposed a huge human and economic cost worldwide. As there are no definitive therapeutic approaches for the disease, the therapeutic potencies of traditional herbal medicines could be helpful to find a solution. Ginger is an ancient medicinal herb which its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties have been known. It consists of several volatile and non-volatile bioactive components whose most bioactivities belong to phenylpropanoids, like gingerols and shogaols. The antioxidant effects of these compounds could create potential protection against infection-induced tissue damages in COVID-19 and other similar viral infections. Ginger compounds can also overexpress Nrf2 as a central down-regulator of the AngII pathway which can reduce the COVID-19 injuries. Moreover, ginger ingredients can modulate the COVID-19-induced inflammation through Th17 over-activation, modulating the macrophages-related responses, down-regulation of pro-inflammatory mediators expression i.e. IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and blocking the NF- κ B activation resulted from AT1R stimulation. Gingerols and shogaols can improve the serum level of lipid profiles. Moreover, ginger compounds can protect the cardiovascular system via anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects. The ginger has also gastrointestinal protective effects through improving the intestinal microbiota as a symbiotic agent. Moreover, it contains antidiarrheal and anti-colic factors that can relieve diarrhea and colic problems in COVID-19 patients. A ginger-enriched enteral diet can also protect the respiratory complications in the patients by decreasing the pro-inflammatory factors such as IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α , and reducing the leukotriene B4 which can decrease vascular permeability. Ginger has also neuroprotective effects by reducing the microglia activation, decreasing the release of nitric oxide, and anti-inflammatory properties. Accordingly, ginger can be considered as a potential therapeutic agent in COVID-19 and other similar infections.

Keywords: Ginger, Molecular aspects, COVID-19, Coronavirus, Infection

Introduction

The novel coronavirus infectious disease (COVID-19) caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) was officially confirmed as a pandemic by World Health Organization (WHO) on 10 April 2020 as the total number of the deaths passed 92000 globally [1]. Coronaviruses are enveloped, positive single-strand RNA viruses that cause respiratory infections in vertebrates, especially in mammals and birds [2, 3]. Before SARS-CoV-2, six members of the Coronaviridae family include HCoV-229E, HCoV-OC43, HCoV-NL63, HKU1, SARS-CoV-1, and MERS-CoV had caused human disease [4]. SARS-CoV-1 and MERS-CoV were responsible of two extensive outbreaks of severe respiratory disease with a high mortality rate during two past decades [5, 6]. The S1 domain of the envelope spike glycoprotein in SARS-CoV-2 is linked with the human CD26. This interaction is a reason for hijacking and virulence by immunoregulatory factors [7]. Molecular analysis showed that SARS-CoV-2 establishes a stronger interaction with angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) than the other viral family members due to its flexible glycy residues within the distinct loop [8]. This could justify the high vulnerability of the virus. Despite efforts to find a cure for COVID-19, health preventive advice and social isolation are currently the only way to control this problem [5]. Trying continues to find the efficient therapeutic options for COVID-19, and some medications like L-Carnitine[9], Losartan and other AT1R blockers [10], and the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug indomethacin [12] have been suggested as potential therapeutic options.

Ginger is a popular spice and ancient medicinal herb which used as a tonic root for over 5000 years, mainly in India, Iranian, and China [11, 12]. Ginger is used for various medical purposes such as treatment of cramps, arthritis and gastrointestinal disorders [13]. Antioxidant, anti-

inflammatory, anti-tumor activities, anti-hyperglycemic, anti-clotting, antidiarrheal, anti-colic, and anti-diabetic are some of ginger properties [14, 15]. Some studies showed the antimicrobial and antiviral effects of ginger [16, 17]. In this review, some potential protective aspects of ginger on COVID-19 have been discussed.

The molecular pathophysiology of COVID-19

The SARS-CoV-2 binds to angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor in the human host cells [18]. The virus-ACE2 interaction facilitates the entrance and replication of the viruses [19]. Angiotensin(Ang)I (Ang1-10) is converted to AngII (Ang1-8) by ACE, but ACE2 converts AngI to Ang1-9. Deactivation of AngII is the critical role of ACE2 by converting it to Ang1-7 [20]. Angiotensin1-7 via the MAS receptor activates the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant pathway in the cell. When SARS-CoV-2 is bound to the ACE2, the ACE/ACE2 ratio is increased, so AngII is attached to the AngII receptor type 1 (AT1R) more than ACE2 [19]. It is the start point of tissue injury because AngII-AT1R attachment triggers a pathway leading to inflammation, reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, vasoconstriction, and fibrosis [21]. ACE2 expression occurs most commonly in the tissues of the lung, liver, kidneys, heart, endothelium, and intestine; so these organs are the most vulnerable organs by coronaviruses [22, 23].

AngII is known as a pro-inflammatory factor whose overexpression significantly contributes to the pathogenesis of chronic hypertension, chronic kidney diseases, heart failure, and other systemic inflammatory diseases via some properties of AngII including vasoconstriction, activating the NADPH oxidase, and overexpression of NF- κ B [24, 25]. NADPH oxidase, a reactive oxygen species (ROS), produces an enzyme with five homologous subgroups in the

human body. NOX1 expression is in epithelial cells, endothelial cells, interstitial fibroblasts, and smooth muscle cells, whereas NOX2 is expressed in phagocytes, vascular cells, heart, kidneys, neurons, and hepatocytes. If these two enzymes are stimulated by AngII, they produce ROS and decrease the available cellular NADPH, under pathological circumstances [26]. This can in turn end in oxidative damage in DNA which is basically repaired through the base excision repair (BER) pathway [27]. Poly-ADP ribose polymerase-1 (PARP-1) plays a significant role in BER and is essential in genomic stability maintenance [28]. PARP-1 has also an antiviral function through the ADP-ribosylation of virus genome (RNA or DNA), an event that inhibits the translation of viral transcripts. Several viral families encode a macrodomain protein with poly (ADP-ribose) glycohydrolase (PARG) function; include Togaviridae, Hepeviridae, and Coronaviridae. This macrodomain may hydrolyze ADP-ribose from proteins and nucleic acids to speed up the viral reproduction and virulence [29].

Ginger potencies against COVID-19 pathology

People usually recognize ginger as a spice with a pungent flavor and warm nature. Nowadays, many people use ginger due to its proven effects on nausea. Ginger consists of several bioactive components, divided into two main groups, volatile and non-volatile compounds. Zingiberene and farnesene are the predominant components of essential oil ginger oleoresin which belong to the sesquiterpene family [30, 31]. Nevertheless, the vast majority of ginger bioactivities belong to phenylpropanoids, like gingerols and shogaols. Gingerols are the most detected phenolic compounds in the fresh ginger including 6-, 8- and 10- gingerols [32]. The results of the phytochemical analysis show that 6-Gingerol is more detectable among other gingerols [30]. Gingerols play a key role in the bioactivities of ginger. However, a dehydrated form of gingerol

named shogaol will be detected in the condition of heat treatment or prolong storage of ginger [32]. Zingerone and gingerdione are also found in this condition with lower amounts. Paradol is a byproduct of shogaol reduction which has anti-cancer effects [30].

6-gingerol and 6-shogaol also play a vital role in the antioxidant properties of ginger. It has been known that these polyphenols can be the cause of *Nrf2* gene upregulation leading to glutathione (GSH) level enhancement [33]. Besides 6-gingerol and 6-shogaol, some studies investigated 8-gingerol as a potent airway smooth muscle relaxant [34, 35] which can potentiate β -agonist-induced relaxation activity [34](1)(Townsend et al., 2014). Zingerone, made from dehydration of gingerol, plays a beneficial role in different parts of the body. It particularly prevents Alzheimer's disease by reducing the reactive nitrogen species [36].

1. Ginger and Antioxidant effects

Phenolic compounds, because of their high redox potential are among the famous antioxidants as they reduce agents, quench singlet oxygen, donate hydrogen, and chelated metal agents [37]. Some isolated types of phenolic compounds from ginger are gingerol, shogaol, paradol, quercetin, zingerone, gingerenone-A, and 6-dehydrogingerdione whose antioxidant effects have been determined [38-40]; a protective property that may decrease infection-induced tissue damages in COVID-19 and other similar viral infections. Figure1

Ginger extract

In an experimental study, the ginger extract showed antioxidant effects in stressed rat heart homogenates. It reduced the level of malondialdehyde (MDA), and in resultant decreased lipid peroxidation [41]. Moreover, the ginger extract could reduce the content of ROS and lipid

peroxidation and increase the gene expression of antioxidant enzymes in human chondrocyte with IL-1 β mediated stress [42]. In H₂O₂-induced oxidative stressed human fibrosarcoma cells, ginger extract decreased the production of ROS [43]. Furthermore, in another study, after chemotherapy with cyclophosphamide, the contents of antioxidants and testosterone increased by treatment with ginger extract [44].

6- Shogol

In human colon cancer cells, 6-shogaol causes Nrf2 translocation into the nucleus and inducing the expression of Nrf2 target genes (*FTL*, *HO-1*, *Trx1*, *TrxR1*, *AKR1B10*, *GCTLA4*, *NQO1*, *GCLM*, and *GCLC*) through modifying Keap1 and protecting Nrf2 from proteasomal degradation. So, this pathway leads to increasing the glutathione level and decreasing the level of ROS [45]. Chen et al [45] studied the effect of 6-shogaol on wild type mice and Nrf2^{-/-} mice too. In the colon of wild-type mice, 6-shogaol revealed antioxidant effect by up-regulating the Nrf2 target genes such as *MT1*, *HO-1*, and *GCLC* but not affect Nrf2^{-/-} mice. 6-shogaol showed antioxidant effects in HepG2 cells against H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress. 6-shogaol caused induced γ -glutamylcysteine synthetase (GCS) and *HO-1* expressions via Nrf2 accumulation in the nucleus and activation of c-jun N-terminal kinase [46].

6- Gingerol

Treatment of human osteoarthritis chondrocytes with 6-gingerol leads to activation of Nrf2, decreased IL-1 β -induced *GSTA4* expression, and prevention of IL-1 β -induced NO, PGE₂, MMP-13, and HNE production [47]. Moreover, 6-gingerol showed antioxidant effects in mice via activating the Nrf2 pathway, and inhibiting the IL-1 β and caspase-1 protein expression [48].

Ginger phenylpropanoids

Treatment of foreskin fibroblast cells with ginger phenylpropanoids induced Nrf2 activity and increased the levels of glutathione S-transferase P1 (GSTP1) [39].

Ginger oleoresin

Ginger oleoresin reduced the ROS level by translocating Nrf2 to the cell nucleus and inducing the expression of *HO-1* and *NQO1* genes in human mesenchymal stem cells [38].

Figure1. The antioxidant molecular pathway of ginger against COVID-19:

Ginger affects the renin-angiotensin system by affecting the Nrf2-Keap1 signaling pathway and upregulating the antioxidant genes like FTL, HO-1, Trx1, TrxR1, AKR1B10, GCTLA4, NQO1, GCLM and GCLC

(AngII: Angiotensin II, ATR1: Angiotensin II receptor type 1, Nrf2: nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2, Keap1: Kelch-like ECH-associated protein, HO-1: heme oxygenase-1, Trx1: thioredoxin 1, TrxR1: Thioredoxin reductase 1, AKR1B10: Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10, GCTLA4: γ -glutamyltransferase-like activity4, NQO1: Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate, GCLM: Glutamate-cysteine ligase modifier subunit, GCLC: Glutamate-cysteine ligase catalytic subunit)

2. Ginger and RAS-modulatory effect

Renin-angiotensin system (RAS) is a key determinant pathway in the pathophysiology of COVID-19 [29, 49, 50]. Intravenous infusions of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) led to an increase in the amount of ACE2 receptors during an in-vivo study. Thus, ACEIs and ARBS may increase the risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection [51]. Based on Diaz [51] hypothesis, blockage of the intracellular AngII cascade may be better therapeutic choices. As we reviewed, Nrf2 is the most important pathway activated by the ginger bioactive components. Many research shows that Nrf2 has a central role in down-regulating the AngII pathway [52-54]. Accordingly, ginger bioactive components can be considered as the therapeutic choices to reduce COVID-19 injuries. Figure1

3. Immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory properties of ginger

The immune response is substantial for the control and eradication of COVID-19 infections [55]. Human antigen presentation cells (APC) engulf the antigenic peptides of the virus, then present by major histocompatibility complex (MHC) or human leukocyte antigen (HLA). Thereafter, the virus is recognized by virus-specific cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) [56]. The Naïve CD4+ T lymphocytes (Th0 cells) are polarized to Th17 cells against various pathogens in the lung [57]. Th17 cells release a different kinds of cytokines such as IL-17 (IL-17A), IL-17F, IL-21, IL-22, IL-23, IL-26, TNF- α , CCL20 [57, 58]. Then IL-17 drives the production of various pro-inflammatory mediators, including IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , CXCL1, CXCL6, CCL2, and G-CSF [57, 59]. Th17 cells have presented both protective and pathogenic roles in the lung [57].

Pulmonary and systemic inflammatory responses are attributed to the spread of COVID-19 infections, which induced by innate immunity [55]. Inflammation is a protective response to host tissue damage and infection. This response coordinates the different signaling pathways regulating pro and anti-inflammatory mediators in host tissue and leukocytes [60]. A massive release of pro-inflammatory cytokines including IFN- α , IFN- γ , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-12, IL-18, IL-33, TNF- α , TGF β , and chemokines (e.g. CCL2, CCL3, CCL5, CXCL8, CXCL9) resulted in a cytokine storm [61]. Moreover, SARS-CoV-2 invades the host cell through the spike protein-ACE2 binding pathway [62]. It leads to the down-regulation of ACE2 (2,3) which naturally converts AngII to Ang(1-7) as an important vasodilator, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory agent (4). This upsets the balance of the RAS and results in the raise of the Ang II/Ang(1-7) ratio as an important leading cause of severe respiratory, cardiac, and renal complications in COVID-19 (3). Under other conditions, AngII as a powerful pro-inflammatory mediator binds to the AngII receptor type 1 (AT1R) and activates NF- κ B [65, 66], and up-regulates the expression of tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , IL-6 and IL-8 [67]. Hence, the imbalance between the ACE/AngII/AT1 receptor pathway and ACE2/Ang(1-7)/MAS receptor pathway in the RAS induces a multi-system inflammation [68].

Therefore, the control of inflammation is essential to prevent lung damage, and fluid/cell accumulation in COVID-19 [55]. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) has potential effects on the treatment of inflammatory disorders, i.e. neurodegenerative disease (multiple sclerosis) [58], cancers (ovarian cancer) [69] and cardiovascular disease (atherosclerosis, chronic heart disease (CHD), and hypertension) [70, 71]. According to previous studies, ginger can induce anti-inflammatory effects through different mechanisms [72]. Kiuchi *et al.* showed the potential effect of the Zingiberaceae family on in-vivo inhibition of prostaglandin [73] and leukotriene

synthesis, the inflammatory mediators created from arachidonic acid through 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX) activation [74]. Over-activation of T cells (e.g. Th17) [75], deregulated inflammatory response [60], and cytokine storm [76] contribute to the severity of COVID-19 outcome, long-lasting tissue damage and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Th17 is associated with the cytokine storm in pulmonary viral infections such as SARS-CoV-2 [77].

On the other hand, ginger extract diminishes the expression of IL-17, IL-6, IL-23, and differentiation of Th17 through the down-regulation of the Th17 cell-related immune response [78, 79]. Gingerol, shogaol, zingerone, paradol, gingerdione, and other active ingredients of ginger inhibit the cyclooxygenase pathway, formation of prostaglandin and leukotriene, and pro-inflammatory cytokine biosynthesis (e.g. IL-1, and IL-8) [74, 80]. In one study, pro-inflammatory genes such as *IL-1 β* , *IL-6* were abolished by ginger extract [81]. Inactivating the NF- κ B was the suggested mechanism for inhibition of the pro-inflammatory gene expression [82]. Rhode *et al* reported that ginger can inhibit IL-8 production and NF- κ B activation in ovarian cancer cell lines [69]. NF- κ B pathway is responsible for IL-1 and TNF α signaling, and cytokines, chemokines, and adhesion molecules genes expression [83]. Habib SHM *et al* indicated that ginger extract significantly decreased the expression of NF- κ B and TNF- α in rats affected by liver cancer [84]. Ginger has also an inhibitory effect on the expression of CCL20 and CCL22 through the suppression of NF- κ B [79]. NF- κ B activation is associated with a variety of inflammatory diseases, including asthma, rheumatoid arthritis, multiple sclerosis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), ulcerative colitis, and atherosclerosis [85].

Tripathi S, et al indicated that ginger extract could inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-12, TNF- α , IL-1 β) by Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) stimulated macrophages and production of IFN- γ and IL-2 by T cells. Also, the ginger extract could inhibit LPS that triggers the activation of macrophage leading to a decrease in T cell proliferation in response to alloantigen [86]. Lantz et al, however, reported an inhibitory effect for gingerols on LPS-induced COX-2 expression while shogaol had no effect on COX-2 expression. It also showed an ingredient found in ginger could inhibit PGE₂ production [87]. Furthermore, ginger inhibits platelet aggregation and platelet prostaglandin-endoperoxides in-vitro [88]. Jung HW et al displayed that the rhizome hexane fraction extract of *Zingiber officinale Roscoe* could inhibit the production of NO, PGE₂, TNF- α , and IL-1 β [89]. Ginger extract can also reduce the serum levels of IgE and protein levels of Th2 type cytokines (IL-4 and IL-5) [90].

Emerging data hypothesize that ginger ingredients have therapeutic potentials in the modulation of COVID-19-induced inflammation via Th17 over activation, modulating the macrophages-related responses, down-regulation of pro-inflammatory mediators expression i.e. IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and blocking the NF- κ B activation resulted from AT1R stimulation. Figure2

4. The Cardioprotective effects of Ginger in COVID-19

COVID-19 as a pandemic disease can directly affect the cardiovascular tract. Patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD) are more susceptible to COVID-19. There is also a higher risk of adverse events for patients with CVD who are superimposed by COVID-19 [91]. Therefore, an efficient therapeutic approach for CVD patients will reduce the mortality of this infection [92].

Figure2. The anti-inflammatory molecular pathway of ginger against COVID-19:

Ginger down-regulates NF-κB which has a vital role in the regulation of several pro-inflammatory genes such as TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-6, IL-8, CXCL1, CXCL6, CCL2, and G-CSF.

(AngII: Angiotensin II, ATR1: Angiotensin II receptor type 1, TNF-α: Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha, IL: Interleukin, CXCL: The chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand, G-CSF: Granulocyte-colony stimulating factor, CCL: Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand)

Dyslipidemia is a common important risk factor for CVD [93]. A systematic review and meta-analysis indicated that ginger can improve the serum level of triacylglycerol (TAG), and Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) [94]. Although some studies have shown no significant effect of ginger supplementation on blood lipid profile [95, 96], gingerols and shogaols as two bioactive components of ginger have presented anti-hyperlipidemic activities in some experimental studies [97, 98].

Arterial inflammation is an important risk factor for CVD which is due to the effects of lipoxygenase and cyclooxygenase enzymes on arachidonic acid and the production of inflammatory mediators [70]. As mentioned, some components of ginger can suppress the prostaglandins and leukotrienes by inhibiting the cyclooxygenase1, cyclooxygenase2, and lipoxygenase enzymes. As a consequence, ginger has anti-inflammatory properties [99].

ROS molecules contribute to the progression of CVD [98]. Ginger has high antioxidant properties and neutralizes free radicals. Moreover, ginger increases the serum levels of antioxidant enzymes and glutathione [70]. As a result, ginger has vasoprotective effects and is considered as a cardioprotective agent [13]. Figure3

Figure3. The potential protective effects of ginger bioactive components against heart failure and pulmonary dysfunction, the most important side effect of COVID-19

5. The gastrointestinal protective effects of Ginger in COVID-19

Gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms, including diarrhea, anorexia, vomiting, and abdominal pain are common in patients with COVID-19. According to the reports, digestive symptoms such as diarrhea can begin even before the respiratory symptoms [100]. Nausea has been also reported as a GI symptom in these patients. Moreover, in the COVID-19 patients with GI symptoms, the incidence of liver damage has been higher than in the patients without GI symptoms [101]. The association between SARS-CoV-2 and liver damage is not fully known, but the increasing inflammation, physiological stress, drug toxicity, and the history of the liver disease can include the liver damage mechanisms in the SARS infection [102].

An imbalance in human microbiota can lead to some respiratory illnesses, such as asthma, COPD, and cystic fibrosis [103]. In patients with respiratory infections such as COVID-19, gut dysfunction due to the relation between lungs and intestine may occur. Thus, adjusting the gut microbiota can be a part of the treatment for the patients with COVID-19 [104]. Jing Wang et al, recently, indicated that *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe could improve the intestinal microbiota in mice by increasing the bacterial species such as subspecies of *Bifidobacterium* [105]. Accordingly, ginger compounds can be considered as the symbiotic agents in the treatment of COVID-19.

Moreover, ginger contains antidiarrheal and anti-colic factors, so it has long been used to treat diarrhea, and colic problems [14]. Dong-Mei Su et al reported that polysaccharides obtained from *Zingiber officinale* rhizome (ZRP) had remarkable antidiarrheal effects in rats with diarrhea caused by folium. In fact, ZRP could modulate the brain-gut peptides, including VIP, CCK, and ghrelin [106]. A systematic review in 2019 also revealed that the ginger effect is more than vitamin B₆ in reducing nausea and vomiting in pregnant women. The anti-nausea properties of the ginger attribute to its two bioactive components, including galanactone and 6-gingerol [107].

6. Ginger and its therapeutic potent for lung injuries in COVID-19

COVID-19 can manifest as asymptomatic pneumonia and acute respiratory disease, in the infected persons [108]. The respiratory failure in the disease occurs due to extensive lung fibrosis. This complication is the most important morbidity and a common cause of death in the disease [109]. The pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 is a huge oxidative stress and a deleterious cytokine storm, as two major pathophysiologic pathways. COVID-19 can also increase pulmonary vascular permeability. This event can lead finally to ARDS [29]. In ARDS, pro-inflammatory mediators such as IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α are increased leading to the accumulation of neutrophils. Neutrophils also release the inflammatory mediators and ROS molecules, causing the destruction of alveolar cells [110, 111]. Figure3

Shariatpanahi et al indicated a ginger-enriched enteral diet in ARDS patients can reduce the pro-inflammatory factors such as IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α . This study also presented a reduction of serum LTB₄ (Leukotriene B₄) levels which leads to an increase the oxidative stress and vascular

permeability. As a result, the length of ICU stay and duration of mechanical ventilation was reduced in these patients [112]. MahmoodKhan et al indicated that ginger extracts can inhibit the inflammation of the respiratory system by blocking the inflammatory mediators (Interleukin 4, 5) of Th2 cells in mice [90]. Moreover, zerumbone that is obtained by steam distillation from wild ginger (*Zingiber zerumbet*) could decrease TNF α and IL-6 which are pro-inflammatory cytokines in mice [113]. Furthermore, *Zingiber officinale* can inhibit the viral attachment and internalization, and may increase the IFN- β secretion, through which *Zingiber officinale* can act against HRSV virus [98].

7. The Neuroprotective effects of ginger in COVID-19

There is growing evidence that the brain could be the main trigger in the severity of COVID-19, but there is a paucity of evidence derived from human patients; so almost always SARS-CoV2 effects on the respiratory system, but the primary pathophysiology behind the respiratory dysfunction and mortality remains elusive. Regarding the previous studies on SARS-CoV infection and other coronaviruses in the nervous system are suggestive that SARS-CoV2 infection may cause respiratory failure by disrupting the cardio-respiratory center in the brainstem, likely through stimulating the ACE2 receptor in the neurons[114]. ACE2 is a bit expressed in the brain, particularly in glial cells and neurons [115].

Ginger has potential effects on the treatment of inflammation [79]. According to some studies, 6-shogaol, a pungent agent from *Zingiber officinale* Roscoecan, can reduce the microglia activation. This agent significantly inhibits the release of nitric oxide (NO) and has anti-neuroinflammatory effects [116, 117].

Many neuronal losses have been found in COVID-19 along with increased inflammatory cytokines, and proliferation of microglia, but not of astrocytes [118]. Additional Studies using transgenic mice demonstrated an enhanced level of IL-6, IL-12p40, G-CSF, CXCL1, MIP-a, and MCP-1 in brain homogenates 3 days after the SARS-CoV infection resulting in an inflammatory cytokine reaction [119]. Such cytokine elevations and extensive neuronal pathologies in the brainstem were also noted in MERS-CoV infections [120]. Ginger with anti-inflammatory properties can reduce IL-6, IL-12 and decrease inflammation in the nervous system [78, 79].

Conclusion

Ginger as an ancient medicinal herb has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and RAS-modulatory properties which can be suggested as a potential protective and therapeutic agent in COVID-19 and other similar infections. Ginger includes bioactive components among which phenylpropanoids, like gingerols and shogaols have the most biochemical effects. Ginger compounds can down-regulate the AngII pathway as an important pro-inflammatory cascade. It also improves the COVID-19-induced inflammation through Th17 over-activation, modulating the cytokine storm, and up-regulation of the NF- κ B signaling pathway. Moreover, ginger compounds have a potential role in protecting the respiratory, cardiac, gastrointestinal, and neurologic complications in COVID-19 via anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects, improving the serum lipid profiles, endothelial function, intestinal microbiota, and vascular permeability whose molecular mechanisms have been clarified in different multiple studies.

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